

Downey et al. "Hay provision affects 24-h performance of normal and abnormal oral behaviors in individually housed dairy calves"

Supplemental Figure 4. Overall proportion of 24-h observations engaged in tongue rolling in wk 2, 4, 6, and 8. Each colored line represents an individual calf. The dashed line represents the start of weaning (50-60 ± 1 d). All wk 8 observations were conducted on d 6 of step-down weaning when the 2nd of 3 milk meals had been removed.